

Bill To:

Hüseyin NAZLIKUL

Specialist in General Medicine and Physical and
Rehabilitation Medicine (PRM)- Medical Biophysics

Hakki Yeten Cad. No 23 Kat 3, Vital Fulya Plaza , TR- 34394 Istanbul - Sisli

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Name of Coauthors: Prof. Dr. Fatma Gülçin Ural Nazlikul, Prof. Dr. Dr. med. Hüseyin Nazlikul

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Salient Visionary Publications LLC

5830 E 2nd St Ste 8

Casper, WY, USA 82609

E-mail: contact@salientvisionarypub.com

Offshore Office

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